

AN EXPERIMENTAL STUDY ON THE IN-SITU STRENGTH OF SiC FIBER IN UNIDIRECTIONAL SiC/Al COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT: In order to investigate the effect of manufacturing process on the mechanical properties of the fiber in the UFRMMC (unidirectional fiber reinforced metal matrix composite), in-situ SiC fiber bundles were extracted from two kinds of SiC/Al composite wires, which were heat-treated at two different temperatures (exposed in the air at 400 °C and 600 °C for 40 minutes after composition). Tensile tests for these two fiber bundles were performed at different strain rates (quasi-static test: 0.001s^{-1} , dynamic test: 200s^{-1} , 700s^{-1} , and 1200s^{-1}) and the stress-strain curves were obtained. The experimental results showed that their mechanical properties are rate-dependent: the modulus E , strength σ_b and ultimate strain ε_b under dynamic state are obviously higher than those under quasi-static state; under the dynamic state, these mechanical parameters all increase with increasing strain rate. The mechanical properties of the in-situ fiber bundles, which were extracted from the composite wires processed at 600 °C, are slightly inferior to those of the in-situ fiber bundles extracted from the composite wires processed at 400 °C. Compared with the original fiber, both of the two in-situ fibers have obvious degradation in the mechanical properties. This can most likely induce a degradation of UFRMMC. A bimodal Weibull statistical constitutive equation was adopted to describe the stress-strain relationship of the two in-situ fiber bundles. The simulated stress-strain curves agree well with the experimental results.

KEYWORDS: strain rate, tensile, SiC fiber, in-situ strength, Weibull

INTRODUCTION

It has been found that the strength of UFRMMC does not reach the value predicted by the rule of mixtures [1, 2]. This has been conjectured to be due to the performance degradation of the in-situ fiber [3, 4], so the properties of UFRMMC should be determined by those of the in-situ fiber (fiber after matrix impregnation), rather than those of the original fiber. Since the fiber is the main load-bearing element in the composites, it is important to get a reliable means to obtain information about the mechanical properties of the in-situ fiber.

Some references have reported that the strength distribution of in-situ fiber can be obtained by etching method and single fiber test [5], but there are shortcomings in this single fiber test. First, it is rather tedious to extract individual fiber from a bundle and to perform numerous tests on single fiber with very small diameter. Second, stronger fibers were “selected” inevitably during the extraction of fiber from a bundle since the weaker ones are prone to damage and fracture in the process. Third, it is difficult to determine the exact cross-sectional area of a single fiber. Chi et al. [6] proposed a procedure for determining the quasi-static properties of single fiber by measuring those of fiber bundles. Xia et al. [7,8] extended the method to the dynamic state and first successfully performed tensile impact test on fiber bundles. Wang et al. [9] established a single Weibull distribution and a bimodal Weibull distribution model for strain rate and temperature-dependent fiber strength. Based on the above etching method and the fiber bundles test, the mechanical behaviours of in-situ SiC fibers under different strain rates are tested and characterized in this paper.

EXPERIMENTAL AND DISCUSSION

1 Testing method

The UFRMMC used in the present paper are two kinds SiC/Al composite wires processed with

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different heat-treatments. The composite wires are produced by the ultrasonic liquid infiltration method [10], then exposed in the air at 400°C and 600°C for 40 minutes, respectively, and cooled to the room temperature. The original fiber bundles used in the composite wire are Nicalon SiC fiber bundle, which are manufactured by Nippon Carbon Co.Ltd, with the trademark NLM202. Each bundle contains 500 fibers and has a cross-sectional area of $8.667 \times 10^{-2} \text{mm}^2$. The density of the fiber is 2.537g/cm^3 . The matrix is an industrial pure aluminum (>99.6 wt% purity), and the volume fraction of fiber in the composite wire is 50%. Quasi-static (strain rate: 0.001s^{-1}) and dynamic tensile test (strain rate: 200s^{-1} , 700s^{-1} and 1200s^{-1}) were performed at a Shimazu DT-5000 testing machine and a self-designed Split Hopkinson Tensile Bar [11], respectively. The specimen and its connection are shown in fig.1.

1. lining block 2. supplement plate 3. composite wires (or in-situ fiber bundles) 4. input bar (or short metal bar) 5. output bar (or short metal bar)

First, the lining blocks (1) are glued on the supplement plate (2) perpendicularly, 9 composite wires (3) are put into the slot of the lining blocks parallel, then the wires are glued to the lining blocks by a high strength adhesive and covered with a metal plate. To extract the fiber from the composite wires, the aluminium matrix is dissolved in a NaOH solution 5% by weight, so that the in-situ fiber bundles specimen is obtained. In order to examine the effect of NaOH on the fiber, a group of original SiC fiber bundles are marinated in the NaOH solution, and then tested under different strain rates. It was found that the stress-strain curves keep unchanged compared with those of the original fiber bundles not marinated in NaOH solution, which means the NaOH solution has no influence on the mechanical properties of SiC fiber. In the quasi-static test, the specimen is glued to the slots of two short metal bars (4) and (5) using the high shear strength adhesive, the short metal bars are clamped by the collets of Shimazu DT-5000 during testing, in the dynamic test, the specimen is glued to the slots at the ends of the input bar (4) and the output bar (5) with the adhesive. The supplement plate is taken off before testing. In the following text, the in-situ fiber extracted from the composite wires heat-treated at 400°C will be referred to as in-situ fiber 1, and the other in-situ fiber extracted from the composite wires heat-treated at 600°C will be referred to as in-situ fiber 2.

2 Experiment results and analysis

Fig.2 Stress strain curves of the two in-situ fiber bundles under different strain rates (a) in-situ fiber

bundles 1 (b) in-situ fiber bundles 2

Tab.1a Mechanical parameters of the in-situ fiber bundles 1 under different strain rates

$E(\text{GPa})$	$ \Delta E/E (\%)$	$\sigma_b(\text{GPa})$	$ \Delta\sigma_b/\sigma_b (\%)$	$\varepsilon_b(\%)$	$ \Delta\varepsilon_b/\varepsilon_b (\%)$	$\dot{\varepsilon}(s^{-1})$
131	2.0	1.25	2.2	1.15	3.3	0.001
159	2.8	1.46	2.4	1.25	3.0	200
166	2.1	1.56	2.3	1.30	2.1	700
168	1.5	1.65	1.6	1.32	2.8	1200

Tab.1b Mechanical parameters of the in-situ fiber bundles 2 under different strain rates

$E(\text{GPa})$	$ \Delta E/E (\%)$	$\sigma_b(\text{GPa})$	$ \Delta\sigma_b/\sigma_b (\%)$	$\varepsilon_b(\%)$	$ \Delta\varepsilon_b/\varepsilon_b (\%)$	$\dot{\varepsilon}(s^{-1})$
130	1.8	1.15	2.5	1.14	2.7	0.001
142	2.1	1.36	1.5	1.26	1.6	200
145	2.5	1.43	2.4	1.29	2.4	700
147	2.7	1.46	2.2	1.31	2.1	1200

Fig3. Mechanical parameters of the two in-situ fiber bundles at different strain rates.

The stress-strain curves of the two in-situ fiber bundles at different strain rates are shown in Fig. 2. The mechanical parameters are shown in Fig.3 and Tab.1. At the strain rate $\dot{\varepsilon} = 0.001s^{-1}$, the integral stress-strain curves are not recorded because of the limit of the recording speed of the Shimazu DT-5000 testing machine. From fig.3 and tab.1 it can be seen that the mechanical properties of the two in-situ fiber bundles are rate-dependent: the modulus E , strength σ_b and ultimate strain ε_b (the strain corresponding to σ_b) under dynamic state are obviously higher than those under quasi-static state; under the dynamic state, the above mechanical parameters all increase with increasing strain rates. Concerning with the heat-treatment temperature effect on the mechanical properties of the in-situ fiber, it can be seen that compared with the mechanical properties of in-situ fiber bundles 1, the ε_b of in-situ fiber bundles 2 changes little at different strain rates, while E and σ_b degrade to a certain extent. Based on these experiment results, an exponential function is used to describe the relationship between these parameters and the strain rate [12]:

$$\sigma_b = \sigma_{b0} \left(\frac{\dot{\varepsilon} + \dot{\varepsilon}_{\sigma}}{\dot{\varepsilon}_0} \right)^{m_{\sigma}} \quad \varepsilon_b = \varepsilon_{b0} \left(\frac{\dot{\varepsilon} + \dot{\varepsilon}_{\varepsilon}}{\dot{\varepsilon}_0} \right)^{m_{\varepsilon}} \quad E = E_0 \left(\frac{\dot{\varepsilon} + \dot{\varepsilon}_{E}}{\dot{\varepsilon}_0} \right)^{m_E} \quad \square\square$$

where $\dot{\varepsilon}, \dot{\varepsilon}_0, \sigma_{b0}, \varepsilon_{b0}$ and E_0 are strain rate, reference strain rate, reference strength and reference modulus, respectively. $m_{\sigma}, m_{\varepsilon}$ and m_E are the strain rate sensitivity coefficients. $\dot{\varepsilon}_{\sigma}, \dot{\varepsilon}_{\varepsilon}$ and $\dot{\varepsilon}_{E}$ are

the transition strain rates. The mechanical properties of SiC fiber is rate-sensitive when strain rate exceed the transition strain rate, while remain unchanged when the strain rate below the transition strain rate. Assuming $\dot{\varepsilon} = 200s^{-1}$, we obtained the simulated curves by using the least squares method :

$$\begin{aligned}
 E_1 &= 159 \left(\frac{\dot{\varepsilon} + 0.42}{200} \right)^{0.0314} & E_2 &= 142 \left(\frac{\dot{\varepsilon} + 1.87}{200} \right)^{0.0189} \\
 \sigma_{b1} &= 1.46 \left(\frac{\dot{\varepsilon} + 18.74}{200} \right)^{0.0656} & \sigma_{b2} &= 1.36 \left(\frac{\dot{\varepsilon} + 2.93}{200} \right)^{0.0397} \\
 \varepsilon_{b1} &= 1.25 \left(\frac{\dot{\varepsilon} + 13.11}{200} \right)^{0.0306} & \varepsilon_{b2} &= 1.26 \left(\frac{\dot{\varepsilon} + 1.78}{200} \right)^{0.0212}
 \end{aligned} \tag{2}$$

where the subscript “1” and “2” represent the fiber bundles 1 and 2, respectively.

Tab.2. Mechanical properties of the original SiC fiber bundles under different strain rates.

$E(GPa)$	$ \Delta E / E $	$\sigma_b(GPa)$	$ \Delta \sigma_b / \sigma_b $	$\varepsilon_B(\%)$	$ \Delta \varepsilon_B / \varepsilon_B $	$\dot{\varepsilon}(s^{-1})$
132	3.0%	1.35	2.2%	1.15	1.7%	10^{-4}
133	2.3%	1.37	1.5%	1.16	2.6%	10^{-3}
166	2.3%	1.85	2.7%	1.26	3.2%	200
172	0.9%	2.05	1.5%	1.38	1.4%	700
175	1.2%	2.19	2.7%	1.45	0.7%	1200

Fig.4 Stress strain curves of the original and the in-situ SiC fiber bundles at $\dot{\varepsilon} = 700s^{-1}$

In order to demonstrated the differences of the mechanical properties between the original fiber and the in-situ fiber, the tensile tests on the original SiC fiber bundles were also performed. It's mechanical parameters are listed in Tab.2, and the stress-strain curves of both the original fiber bundles and the in-situ fiber bundles at strain-rate $700s^{-1}$ are drawn in fig.4. Compared with the properties of original fiber bundles, it can be seen that the strength σ_b of the in-situ fiber bundles obviously degrade at all strain rates; the modulus E changed little at the quasi-static state and degrade obviously at the dynamic state; the ultimate strain ε_b changed little at the quasi-static state and degrade slightly at the dynamic state.

Since the fiber is the main load-bearing element in the composites, the degradation of the in-situ fiber strength will inevitably induce the degradation of UFRMMC. In conclusion a reliable testing method for the properties of in-situ fiber is essential to understand the mechanical behaviours of UFRMMC.

3 Statistical analysis of the in-situ fiber

In order to characterize the strength distribution and the strain rate dependent properties of the in-situ

fiber, the statistical model proposed by Wang et al. [9] is adopted to describe the stress-strain relationship of the fiber bundles. Based on the above experiment results, the Weibull probability plots of the two in-situ fibers are drawn in fig.5. It can be seen from fig.5 that the Weibull plot of SiC fiber appear approximately bi-linear under high strain rates, which means there are probably two kinds of strength-limiting defect populations existing together in the SiC fiber[13,14]. Hence, a bi-modal Weibull model is adopted here to describe the strength distribution of the in-situ fiber .

The damage constitutive equation for fiber bundles is given as following:

$$\sigma = E\varepsilon \exp \left[- \left(\frac{E\varepsilon}{\sigma_{01}} \right)^{\beta_1} - \left(\frac{E\varepsilon}{\sigma_{02}} \right)^{\beta_2} \right] \quad (3)$$

where β_1 and β_2 are the shape parameters, and σ_{01} and σ_{02} are the scale parameters. These four parameters can be determined by the regression analysis method [9] with the experimental data, their values are listed in tab.3.

Tab.3 Weibull parameters for in-situ fibers under different strain rates

rate	in-situ fiber 1				in-situ fiber 2			
	σ_{01}	β_1	σ_{02}	β_2	σ_{01}	β_1	σ_{02}	β_2
0.001	2.85	2.62	2.00	13.94	2.64	2.44	1.90	14.96
200	3.20	2.59	2.60	14.02	3.10	2.44	2.27	15.02
700	3.42	2.57	2.87	13.98	3.30	2.46	2.38	15.03
1200	3.65	2.62	2.98	13.95	3.40	2.46	2.52	14.98

From tab.3, it can be seen that the shape parameters change little under different strain rates, while the scale parameters increase with increasing strain rate and cater for the following exponential function:

For the in-situ fiber 1:

$$\sigma_{01} = 3.20 \left(\frac{\dot{\varepsilon} + 38.05}{200} \right)^{0.0698} \quad \sigma_{02} = 2.60 \left(\frac{\dot{\varepsilon} + 6.51}{200} \right)^{0.0766} \quad (4)$$

For the in-situ fiber 2:

$$\sigma_{01} = 3.10 \left(\frac{\dot{\varepsilon} + 8.73}{200} \right)^{0.0513} \quad \sigma_{02} = 2.27 \left(\frac{\dot{\varepsilon} + 7.73}{200} \right)^{0.0547} \quad (5)$$

Submitting the average values of β_1 and β_2 , and the simulated relations of E (in equation 2), σ_{01} and σ_{02} (in equation 4 and equation 5) into equation 3, the constitutive equations of the two in-situ fibers bundles can be obtained. The dashed lines in fig.1 are the simulated curves, which fit the experiment results well,

CONCLUSIONS

- Tensile experiments on the in-situ SiC fiber bundles extracted from two composite wires (exposed in the air at 400 °C and 600 °C for 40 minutes after composition) were carried out at different strain rates (quasi-static test: 0.001 s⁻¹, dynamic test: 200 s⁻¹, 700 s⁻¹ and 1200 s⁻¹). The results showed that the mechanical properties of the two in-situ fiber bundles are rate-dependent: the modulus E, strength σ_b and ultimate strain ε_b under dynamic state are obviously higher than those under quasi-static state; under the dynamic state, these mechanical parameters all increase with increasing strain rates. Concerning with the effect of the heat-treatment temperatures, it was found that compared with the mechanical properties of the in-situ fiber bundles 1, the ultimate strain ε_b of in-situ fiber bundles 2 keeps unchanged at different strain rates, while the modulus E and strength σ_b degrade to a certain extent.
- Compared with the original fiber bundle, the in-situ fiber bundle have obvious degradation in the strength at all the testing strain rates, this will inevitably induce the degradation of UFRMMC.
- The statistical analysis showed that the strength distributions of the two in-situ fibers follow the bimodal Weibull distribution, the bimodal Weibull statistical constitutive relationship can well describe stress-strain relationship of the in-situ fiber bundles.

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